

Transparency Guidelines for Human-Centered Security and Privacy Research

Jan H. Klemmer, Juliane Schmüser, Jacques Suray, Jan-Ulrich Holtgrave, Byron M. Lowens, Florian Schaub, and Sascha Fahl

v0.2, November 04, 2025

Request for Feedback

This is a working paper of transparency guidelines for human-centered security and privacy research papers, on which we hope to collect as much community feedback as possible. Any feedback and comments are therefore appreciated, to ensure that these guidelines are relevant in practice.

About the guidelines

Transparent research reporting is crucial to make research understandable and replicable. The idea of this document is to provide guidelines for the usable privacy and security community on how to report our research transparently. Its focus is therefore human-subject security and privacy studies. SoKs/SLRs are not explicitly covered, though many items still apply - see the [PRISMA statement](#) for explicit reporting guidelines. These guidelines are based on research on the community's research reporting expectations and practices [[Klemmer et al.](#), [Klemmer et al.](#)] and a [workshop held at SOUPS 2025](#).

The goal is to serve as a checklist for both authors and reviewers, ensuring that critical details are included in a paper. The guidelines aim to strengthen research quality further, improve replicability, and support newcomers in participating in our research community, both as authors and reviewers.

How should these guidelines be used?

- In general: This document provides two overview checklists with brief descriptions, one sorted by topic and one sorted by priority. Both link to more extensive descriptions for each criterion.
- As an author: When designing and conducting your research and writing your paper, see what transparency criteria are relevant to your project. The guidelines provide instructions and examples that offer inspiration and can be adapted to a specific paper.
- As a reviewer: When reviewing papers, you can check with these guidelines whether something is missing and should be added to a paper. Reviewers can reference these guidelines in their review to substantiate their critique and point authors to these guidelines for improving a paper's reporting.
- These guidelines should apply to the majority of papers, providing helpful advice on research reporting. However, there may be exceptional cases and exceptions that

necessitate deviating from widely accepted practices. Therefore, these guidelines should be considered in the context of the respective paper.

- These guidelines **do not** aim to prescribe how research should be conducted or should (not) be done in a research project. Instead, they aim to guide papers to report details that allow reviewers and others to assess the merit and rigor of the study and its execution.

What is transparency?

For research and its reporting, we define transparency as follows:

Transparency: Reporting all relevant details, especially methodological details and artifacts, needed to (1) assess the validity of a study and its results and (2) to re-run reported studies independently.

This aligns with the [definition of the US Academy of Sciences](#).

Contributors

- **Timo Jagusch, University of Bonn**
- **Anna-Marie Ortloff, University of Bonn, ORCID: 0000-0002-5735-178X**
- **Lukas Struck, University of Bonn, ORCID: 0000-0001-5613-0646**
- **Jenny Tang, Carnegie Mellon University, ORCID: 0009-0003-2840-1535**

This guideline contains valuable input and feedback that we gathered at the [Workshop on Developing Research Transparency Guidelines in Human-centered Privacy and Security](#) at SOUPS 2025.

Used Terms

Priority

- *Required*: All studies the criterion applies to are expected to provide the respective information. If the information is not provided, a detailed and strong justification for omission is required. Examples for such justification are provided in the detailed description of criteria under “Reasons to Omit”.
- *Strongly Recommended*: Authors are strongly encouraged to include this information to ensure research clarity and assessability, or justify why they cannot include it.
- *Recommended*: Authors are encouraged to provide this information.

Reporting Location

- *In a dedicated (sub)section*: The information should have a clearly marked (sub)section for easy findability.
- *Within a xxx section*: The information should be contained within the specified section (e.g., methodology), but does not warrant its own heading.
- *Within the appendix*: The information or material should be reported in a paper's appendix.
- *As part of supplementary materials*: The information or materials should be a part of a supplementary materials package in a suitable file format. The package should be hosted and published using an archival platform that assigns DOIs (such as the paper publisher, OSF or Zenodo).
A link to the package as well as a description of its content should be included in a dedicated section directly before the references for easy findability. Authors can point to this section when referencing materials throughout the paper.

Overview by Priority

	Title	Description	Applicable Studies
	Required		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Goal & Method Choice	Explain the study objectives, the associated research questions, and the methods chosen to achieve/answer them.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Limitations & Threats to Validity	Describe limitations of the paper and its methodology, and threats to validity that result from the study design.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Protocol	Provide a study protocol that contains a description of all steps of the study execution and the order in which they were performed.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Condition Assignment	Describe how conditions were assigned.	Experimental studies with multiple conditions.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Duration	Describe how long the study or study sessions took, i.e., how long participants were involved, how long a measurement took, or the duration of data collection (if talking about the whole study).	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ethics	Include a section describing the ethical implications of the research, as well as any mitigations of risks or negative impact.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	IRB/ERB	State whether an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics review board (ERB) (in some organizations those boards might have different names) reviewed the study and what the outcome was.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Consent	Describe if and how participants' consent for research participation was obtained, and provide details.	Studies with participants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Compensation	State if, how, and how much participants were compensated.	Studies with participants.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding & Conflicts of Interest	Declare who funded the project, as well as any other conflicts of interest.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sampled Population	Description of the target population that the study addresses and draws its sample from.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sample Description/Demographics	Describe any sample(s) used in analyses, including important sample characteristics such as demographic information.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Recruitment Approach/Sampling Strategy	Describe the procedure(s) with which the study's participants were recruited, or otherwise the means through which the data set was acquired. Include changes made to the approach during the study.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sample Size	State the sample size of a study, i.e., the number of valid participants/data points.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Experiment Materials	Describe all materials and infrastructure used to conduct experiments, including tested interventions.	Experiment studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Interview Guide	Describe and provide the interview guide or protocol used to conduct interviews during the research study.	All studies involving qualitative interviews or (semi-)structured discussions/focus groups.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Questionnaire/Survey Instrument	Describe and provide all materials used to conduct experiments or interventions. This includes tasks, instructions, scripts, prototypes, software, hardware, or any other tools used as part of the study protocol.	Studies with surveys or questionnaires.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Data Preprocessing	Describe how data was preprocessed prior to analysis, including transcription, translation, and anonymization.	Qualitative studies

<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Data Analysis Procedure	Outline the methods and steps of the analysis procedure, and the role of the involved researchers.	Qualitative Studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Analysis Reliability	Discuss how reliability was ensured, such as handling disagreements among researchers, calculating Inter-rater Reliability (IRR), or coding consistency or explain why IRR was not reported.	Qualitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Empirical Evidence	Provide empirical evidence (e.g., quotes, field notes, excerpts, photographs) to support results.	Qualitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative Data Preprocessing	Describe any treatment of raw data prior to analysis, including outlier removal, variable transformation, data quality control.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative Data Analysis Procedure	Outline the methods and steps of the analysis procedure, including statistical tests.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Variables	Name and define all variables that are considered in the statistical analysis, and clearly label them as dependent or independent for each analysis they are a part of.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hypotheses	Explicitly state hypotheses for studies that use confirmatory inferential statistics.	Quantitative studies with confirmatory inferential statistics.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Assumptions	State assumptions made for analyses, and how you tested or justified them.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Descriptive Statistics	Provide measures that describe your data set, such as a mean or median for the central tendency, a measure for variability, or percentages for categorical data.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Statistical Results	Report results of all statistical tests performed.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Confidence/Significance Measure	Provide measures for the statistical significance and confidence of statistical results.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Report and Interpret Effect Sizes	Report and interpret effect sizes of statistical results.	Quantitative studies
	Strongly Recommended		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Approach to LLMs/AI	Describe if and how LLMs or other AI tools were used in the project.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Piloting	Provide information about piloting and testing of the study protocol, as well as any associated adjustments.	Studies with participants.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Context	Describe the context in which the study was conducted, including time, setting, and language(s).	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vulnerability Disclosure	Describe if and how any vulnerabilities discovered during the research were disclosed.	Studies that discovered vulnerabilities
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sampling Materials	Provide the materials used for sampling/recruiting (e.g., recruitment emails or posts, scraping scripts).	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sample Size Justification	Describe how the sample size number was arrived at, with references or reasoning explained (e.g., data saturation, power analysis).	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Codebook	Provide the final codebook.	Qualitative studies
	Recommended		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Consent Form	Provide the consent form used to collect written consent from participants.	Studies with

			participants that used written consent.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Anonymization/De-identification	Report utilized methods of data anonymization, de-identification or pseudonymization when applied to PII or otherwise sensitive data. This does not only apply to full datasets, but can also be necessary for aggregate data (e.g., demographics tables) or excerpts of data (e.g., a detailed quote from an interview) that might otherwise allow identifying someone. Both methods that are only used on published data and those used on all data before analysis should be described.	Studies that collect PII or otherwise sensitive data.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sampling Success Rate	If possible, provide numbers for the success of their sampling strategy, including number of invitations sent, accepted, rejected, and ignored, as well as drop-out rates during the study.	Studies with applicable sampling strategies.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data	Provide the data collected during the study, ideally complete, raw data, or aggregated or anonymized data if necessary.	All
<input type="checkbox"/>	Analyzed Software	Describe, and when possible, provide access to the source code of any software developed, modified, or used during research, including dependencies, configurations, and version information.	All studies involving software tools, algorithms, or user facing systems.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Analyzed Hardware	Specify and provide the details of any specialized hardware or devices used, developed, or modified in the research, enabling others to replicate or build upon the work.	Studies that depend on specific hardware or use custom or modified hardware.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Analysis Software	Share what software was used for data analysis.	Qualitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative Analysis Software	Provide (self-written) code and scripts or specifications of third-party software used for data analysis.	Quantitative studies using software to analyze their data
<input type="checkbox"/>	Correlations	Describe correlations between the observed variables.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Explain Effect Sizes	Explain effect sizes of statistical results.	Quantitative Studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Insignificant Results	Report statistically non-significant results.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Pre-Registration	Pre-registering a study includes submitting a description of the research design, procedures, potential hypotheses and intended methods for data analysis before beginning the study execution. The description is immutable after finalization. Changes might be possible, but need to be traceable.	Quantitative studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Positionality Statement	Provide information about the authors' domain-relevant characteristics, experiences, privileges, and reflections that may influence how they shape the research design or interpret the results.	All

Overview by Topic

	Title	Description	Applicable Studies	Priority
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Design			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Goal & Method Choice	Explain the study objectives, the associated research questions, and the methods chosen to achieve/answer them.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Limitations & Threats to Validity	Describe limitations of the paper and its methodology, and threats to validity that result from the study design.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Approach to LLMs/AI	Describe if and how LLMs or other AI tools were used in the project.	All	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Protocol	Provide a study protocol that contains a description of all steps of the study execution and the order in which they were performed.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Condition Assignment	Describe how conditions were assigned.	Experimental studies with multiple conditions.	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Piloting	Provide information about piloting and testing of the study protocol, as well as any associated adjustments.	Studies with participants.	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Context	Describe the context in which the study was conducted, including time, setting, and language(s).	All	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Duration	Describe how long the study or study sessions took, i.e., how long participants were involved, how long a measurement took, or the duration of data collection (if talking about the whole study).	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Pre-Registration	Pre-registering a study includes submitting a description of the research design, procedures, potential hypotheses and intended methods for data analysis before beginning the study execution. The description is immutable after finalization. Changes might be possible, but need to be traceable.	Quantitative studies	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Positionality Statement	Provide information about the authors' domain-relevant characteristics, experiences, privileges, and reflections that may influence how they shape the research design or interpret the results.	All	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ethical Considerations			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ethics	Include a section describing the ethical implications of the research, as well as any mitigations of risks or negative impact.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	IRB/ERB	State whether an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics review board (ERB) (in some organizations those boards might have different names) reviewed the study and what the outcome was.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Consent	Describe if and how participants' consent for research participation was obtained, and provide details.	Studies with participants	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Consent Form	Provide the consent form used to collect written consent from participants.	Studies with participants that used written consent.	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study Compensation	State if, how, and how much participants were compensated.	Studies with participants.	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vulnerability Disclosure	Describe if and how any vulnerabilities discovered during the research were disclosed.	Studies that discovered vulnerabilities.	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Anonymization/De-identification	Report utilized methods of data anonymization, de-identification or pseudonymization when applied to PII or otherwise sensitive data. This does not only apply to full datasets, but can also be necessary for aggregate data (e.g., demographics tables) or excerpts of data (e.g., a detailed quote from an interview) that might otherwise allow identifying someone. Both methods that are only used on published data and those used on all data before analysis should be described.	Studies that collect PII or otherwise sensitive data.	Recommended

<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding & Conflicts of Interest	Declare who funded the project, as well as any other conflicts of interest.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/> Sampling				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sampled Population	Description of the target population that the study addresses and draws its sample from.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sample Description/Demographics	Describe any sample(s) used in analyses, including important sample characteristics such as demographic information.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Recruitment Approach/Sampling Strategy	Describe the procedure(s) with which the study's participants were recruited, or otherwise the means through which the data set was acquired. Include changes made to the approach during the study.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sampling Materials	Provide the materials used for sampling/recruiting (e.g., recruitment emails or posts, scraping scripts).	All	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sampling Success Rate	If possible, provide numbers for the success of their sampling strategy, including number of invitations sent, accepted, rejected, and ignored, as well as drop-out rates during the study.	Studies with applicable sampling strategies.	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sample Size	State the sample size of a study, i.e., the number of valid participants/data points.	All	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sample Size Justification	Describe how the sample size number was arrived at, with references or reasoning explained (e.g., data saturation, power analysis).	All	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/> Study Instruments & Materials				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Experiment Materials	Describe all materials and infrastructure used to conduct experiments, including tested interventions.	Experiment studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Interview Guide	Describe and provide the interview guide or protocol used to conduct interviews during the research study.	All studies involving qualitative interviews or (semi-)structured discussions/focus groups.	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Questionnaire/Survey Instrument	Describe and provide all materials used to conduct experiments or interventions. This includes tasks, instructions, scripts, prototypes, software, hardware, or any other tools used as part of the study protocol.	Studies with surveys or questionnaires.	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data	Provide the data collected during the study, ideally complete, raw data, or aggregated or anonymized data if necessary.	All	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Analyzed Software	Describe, and when possible, provide access to the source code of any software developed, modified, or used during research, including dependencies, configurations, and version information.	All studies involving software tools, algorithms, or user facing systems.	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Analyzed Hardware	Specify and provide the details of any specialized hardware or devices used, developed, or modified in the research, enabling others to replicate or build upon the work.	Studies that depend on specific hardware or use custom or modified hardware.	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative Analysis & Results				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Data Preprocessing	Describe how data was preprocessed prior to analysis, including transcription, translation, and anonymization.	Qualitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Data Analysis Procedure	Outline the methods and steps of the analysis procedure, and the role of the involved researchers.	Qualitative Studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Analysis Software	Share what software was used for data analysis.	Qualitative studies	Recommended

<input type="checkbox"/>	Qualitative Analysis Reliability	Discuss how reliability was ensured, such as handling disagreements among researchers, calculating Inter-rater Reliability (IRR), or coding consistency or explain why IRR was not reported.	Qualitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Codebook	Provide the final codebook.	Qualitative studies	Strongly Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Empirical Evidence	Provide empirical evidence (e.g., quotes, field notes, excerpts, photographs) to support results.	Qualitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Analysis & Results				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative Data Preprocessing	Describe any treatment of raw data prior to analysis, including outlier removal, variable transformation, data quality control.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative Data Analysis Procedure	Outline the methods and steps of the analysis procedure, including statistical tests.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative Analysis Software	Provide (self-written) code and scripts or specifications of third-party software used for data analysis.	Quantitative studies using software to analyze their data	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Variables	Name and define all variables that are considered in the statistical analysis, and clearly label them as dependent or independent for each analysis they are a part of.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hypotheses	Explicitly state hypotheses for studies that use confirmatory inferential statistics.	Quantitative studies with confirmatory inferential statistics.	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Assumptions	State assumptions made for analyses, and how you tested or justified them.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Descriptive Statistics	Provide measures that describe your data set, such as a mean or median for the central tendency, a measure for variability, or percentages for categorical data.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Correlations	Describe correlations between the observed variables.	Quantitative studies	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Statistical Results	Report results of all statistical tests performed.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Confidence/Significance Measure	Provide measures for the statistical significance and confidence of statistical results.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Report and Interpret Effect Sizes	Report and interpret effect sizes of statistical results.	Quantitative studies	Required
<input type="checkbox"/>	Explain Effect Sizes	Explain effect sizes of statistical results.	Quantitative studies	Recommended
<input type="checkbox"/>	Insignificant Results	Report statistically non-significant results.	Quantitative studies	Recommended

Study Design

Research Goal & Method Choice

Description	Explain the study objectives, the associated research questions, and the methods chosen to achieve/answer them.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Research objectives, questions, and general methods tell readers what to expect from the paper and are essential information that provide context for the method details and results.
How-to	State the objectives and research questions with short explanations. Briefly address what is the genre or type of study that you decided to pursue to accomplish the objectives, and why the design is appropriate for this. References are encouraged.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the paper's abstract (shortly) and introduction.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In this paper, we investigate the following research questions: RQ1: [...]. RQ2: [...]. To answer these questions, we conduct a [type of study].</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Limitations & Threats to Validity

Description	Describe limitations of the paper and its methodology, and threats to validity that result from the study design.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Limitations of the methods provide context to the results and outline how they can and cannot be interpreted without coming to conclusions that are not supported by the chosen method.
How-to	Contextualize the research and discuss alternative design decisions for the study design that might have yielded different results and may represent avenues of future work. Also discuss procedural risks and biases.
Preferred Reporting Location	A dedicated subsection in the methodology or discussion section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	All study designs have limitations, and transparently disclosing and discussing them should not lead to disadvantages for authors.

Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Approach to LLMs/AI

Description	Describe if and how LLMs or other AI tools were used in the project.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	The use of LLMs or AI tools in study design and execution as well as paper writing should be disclosed to give context to readers.
How-to	Briefly state which tool was used for what and how.
Preferred Reporting Location	A dedicated subsection in the methodology section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	The use of LLMs and AI tools does not have to be problematic in and of itself, but should be transparently disclosed, and potential influences and limitations should be considered and discussed.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Study Protocol

Description	Provide a study protocol that contains a description of all steps of the study execution and the order in which they were performed.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	Not all studies follow a rigid study protocol. For some approaches, like grounded theory, it might be more suitable to describe the research process.
Priority	Required
Justification	The study protocol details the methodology and is necessary to understand, assess, analyze, and replicate the method.
How-to	Explain all steps of the study in detail.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the methodology section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Condition Assignment

Description	Describe how conditions were assigned.
Applicable Study Types	Experimental studies with multiple conditions.
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	The description of how the study conditions were assigned is essential for replication and interpretation of the results.
How-to	Describe clearly how different conditions look like and are controlled within the study and how the condition assignment took place. Explicitly state whether participants are assigned to more than one condition in studies with repeated measures.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the methodology section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“The study employed a within-subject design. Participants tested a set of four conditions for one week each, resulting in a total study length of four weeks. The order of conditions was counterbalanced”.</i> – Communicating Device Confidence Level and Upcoming Re-Authentications in Continuous Authentication Systems on Mobile Devices, SOUPS 2019 • <i>“Next, participants were randomly assigned to one of three groups (video, text, control).”</i> – Comparing the Effectiveness of Text-based and Video-based Delivery in Motivating Users to Adopt a Password Manager, EUROUSEC 2021
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Study Piloting

Description	Provide information about piloting and testing of the study protocol, as well as any associated adjustments.
Applicable Study Types	Studies with participants.
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	To assess whether participants understood the tasks or questions, it is important to describe whether piloting took place and the extent to which changes were made as a result.
How-to	Provide information about the procedure, sample size, and sample composition of the pilot study, changes made between the pilot study and the formal study, and what researchers learned from the pilot.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the methodology section.
Example	—

Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Study Context

Description	Describe the context in which the study was conducted, including time, setting, and language(s).
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	The context and environment a study takes place in can have significant influence on results and are thus needed to interpret them.
How-to	Explain the context of the conducted study and any factors that may have influenced participants or measurements, including, for example, the temporal context (e.g., year, time span of the evaluation/data collection), the setting in which the study took place (e.g., online or in-person), what language(s) the study was conducted in, and how any translations were handled.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the methodology section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Study Duration

Description	Describe how long the study or study sessions took, i.e., how long participants were involved, how long a measurement took, or the duration of data collection (if talking about the whole study).
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	This is important to evaluate how long the study actually lasted, how high the burden on participants was, and the extent to which participants were discouraged by the duration.
How-to	Report an average duration and variability.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the methodology section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“To this end, we designed our surveys for experts to complete within 25–30 minutes of focused effort, in line with suggested</i>

	<i>best practices [35]. Actual completion time averaged 27.9 minutes ($\sigma = 2.4$ minutes).” – Above and Beyond: Organizational Efforts to Complement U.S. Digital Security Compliance Mandates, NDSS 2022</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	The study (session) duration does not include time researchers spend on analysis.
Further resources	—

Pre-Registration

Description	Pre-registering a study includes submitting a description of the research design, procedures, potential hypotheses and intended methods for data analysis before beginning the study execution. The description is immutable after finalization. Changes might be possible, but need to be traceable.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Recommended
Justification	The goal is to make research outcomes less malleable (e.g., avoiding <i>p-value hacking</i>) and help identify non-significant research outcomes that need to be reported.
How-to	The pre-registration will be an external submission that the paper should contain a link to. Describe and justify any changes between the pre-registered and actual method.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the methodology section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	It is common to have to adapt to unexpected circumstances in research, and deviation from the pre-registered method should not be seen as negative as long as it is reported, well justified, and does not interfere with the research’s integrity.
Other remarks	Examples for pre-registration options include https://figshare.com/ , OSF , Aspredicted
Further resources	—

Positionality Statement

Description	Provide information about the authors’ domain-relevant characteristics, experiences, privileges, and reflections that may influence how they shape the research design or interpret the results.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	The implementation and results are less susceptible to bias that emerges from the authors’ points of view, e.g. a large-scale closed-ended online survey, or the subject matter or domain does not

	involve a sensitive population, e.g. a comparison of mainstream password-management tools using task analysis.
Priority	Recommended
Justification	The goal is to be transparent about how the authors, their experiences, and their point of view may have shaped the research to provide context to the paper.
How-to	The statement should address the authors' background and relationship to the research topic, their identities and potential biases, a discussion of power dynamics among the study team and the participants and their communities, strategies for mitigating biases and ensuring ethical conduct, and explicit statements of how the positionality has impacted on research design and findings. If you omit information to preserve anonymity during the review process, remember to add it for the final publication.
Preferred Reporting Location	A dedicated subsection in the methodology or discussion section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>As researchers, we recognize that our personal and professional backgrounds inevitably shape our work on [topic in usable security and privacy]. Our expertise in [e.g., human-computer interaction, social psychology, governmental policy work] and our experience in [e.g., industry, advocacy] lead us to prioritize [these specific practices]. We acknowledge that our perspectives may introduce biases, such as [e.g., a focus on technical solutions or a specific user group]. To mitigate this, we have [e.g., employed a diverse research team of xxx, used a xxx approach, engaged in continuous self-reflection via xxx]. Our goal is to be transparent about our positionality so that readers can better understand the context in which this research was conducted and the participants' data interpreted.</i> • <i>The team ranged in experience from novices to researchers with 10 years' experience. The first author, a former practitioner in the study domain, is a Phd student in HCI who led interviews and questionnaires, while the second and third authors assisted in qualitative coding and statistical analysis, and the fourth and fifth authors are the advisors and principal investigators for the project.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	Positionality statements may have to be vague in certain aspects and should not be used to try to identify authors during the review process. Disclosing a position in relation to the research should also not be held against the authors, since it is helpful context for interpreting a paper that authors should be encouraged to share.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Sections 7 and 8 in "Different Researchers, Different Results? Analyzing the Influence of Researcher Experience and Data Type During Qualitative Analysis of an Interview and Survey Study on Security Advice" . CHI. 2023 Kale, Kay and Hullman (2019) Decision-Making Under Uncertainty in Research Synthesis: Designing for the Garden of Forking Paths . CHI 2019

Ethical Considerations

Ethics

Description	Include a section describing the ethical implications of the research, as well as any mitigations of risks or negative impact.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Conducting research ethically and outlining ethical considerations is important to prevent unintended or inappropriate harm to participants, researchers, or third parties. Describing ethics ensures it has been considered, benefits and harms resulting from a research project have been weighed, and helps alleviate concerns that reviewers and readers might have.
How-to	Outline ethical challenges, potential harm, and related considerations, e.g., how those were mitigated or why they are outweighed by the research's benefits. This includes ethical considerations of the study design, execution, and results and their impact, and should highlight implications and mitigations.
Preferred Reporting Location	A dedicated ethics subsection in the paper's methodology section or a dedicated section at the end of the paper if the conference allows/requires that.
Example	— (highly dependent on study) Example from a study with publicly available social media data: "This study does not constitute human subjects research because it exclusively analyzes publicly available data [9, 41]. However, we acknowledge that Redditors did not explicitly consent to the use of their posts for research purposes. All usernames, direct links, and identifiable metadata (e.g., timestamps granular to the hour) were permanently removed during data processing. Furthermore, while the dataset was aggregated and analyzed at scale, we will not publicly release the raw data and destroy our copy, as even anonymized posts could theoretically be traced back to original usernames, potentially exposing user identities [20, 42, 59]. To further protect user identities, excerpts mentioned in the paper have been paraphrased or re-worded so that a reverse search will not identify the post [43], following best practices [56] followed in the usable security and privacy community in reporting user data (https://www.workshopononlineabuse.com/policies.html "); in Victims, Vigilantes, and Advice Givers: An Analysis of Scam-Related Discourse on Reddit, SOUPS 2025
Reviewer Guidance	Authors should discuss ethical implications of study design, execution, results, and result impact. The discussion can be very brief if there are no specific associated risks.
Other remarks	The <i>Menlo Report</i> provides helpful guidance on research ethics.
Further resources	"Ethics in Computer Security Research: A Data-Driven Assessment of the Past, the Present, and the Possible Future", CCS, 2025 https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity26/call-for-papers#ethics

	The Menlo Report "Common Pitfalls in Writing about Security and Privacy Human Subjects Experiments, and How to Avoid Them", SOUPS, 2010 "Flawed, but like democracy we don't have a better system": The Experts' Insights on the Peer Review Process of Evaluating Security Papers", IEEE S&P, 2022
--	---

IRB/ERB

Description	State whether an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics review board (ERB) (in some organizations those boards might have different names) reviewed the study and what the outcome was.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	IRBs/ERBs provide an independent review of research, and knowing whether such a review was conducted and what the outcome was can provide context for reviewers' and readers' evaluation of the research ethics.
How-to	Outline whether IRB/ERB review was obtained. If yes, say what the outcome was. If not, explain why a review was not necessary or not possible (e.g., institution has no ERB) and how ethical research conduct was ensured.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within a dedicated ethics (sub)section (see Ethics).
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of ABC Hospital (Approval #IRB2022-xxx).</i> • <i>The study was reviewed by the Institutional Review Board of XYZ University and was deemed exempt under category 4 for secondary research using publicly available data.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	Research should not be rejected because a review was not possible – instead, the authors' description of their ethical considerations should be used to determine if the project was conducted ethically.
Other remarks	The <i>Menlo Report</i> provides helpful guidance on research ethics. IRBs/ERBs should not be confused with ethics committees at conferences.)
Further resources	"Ethics in Computer Security Research: A Data-Driven Assessment of the Past, the Present, and the Possible Future", CCS, 2025 "Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022", CHI, 2023 "Common Pitfalls in Writing about Security and Privacy Human Subjects Experiments, and How to Avoid Them", SOUPS, 2010 "A Systematic Literature Review of Empirical Methods and Risk Representation in Usable Privacy and Security Research", ACM ToCHI, 2021 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Consent

Description	Describe if and how participants' consent for research participation was obtained, and provide details.
Applicable Study Types	Studies with participants
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	It is important for both reviewers and readers to know if and how consent was obtained (e.g., for ethical clarity and as it might influence participant behavior or create a selection bias).
How-to	Describe the type of consent obtained (e.g., informed, written, none/deception...), what exactly the participants consented to (e.g. audio/video recording), and if any kind of deception study design was involved, include a description of the debriefing.
Preferred Reporting Location	In a dedicated ethics (sub)section or subsection (see Ethics), or Within a (sub)section that describes the recruitment or study procedure that consent was a part of.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>"All participants provided written informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study."</i> • <i>"Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants."</i> • <i>"Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participating minors, and assent was obtained from children aged 7 and older."</i> • <i>"The requirement for informed consent was waived by the IIRB due to the retrospective nature of the study and use of anonymized data."</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	If a consent form was used, providing it can provide details and clarity.
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022", CHI, 2023 "A Systematic Literature Review of Empirical Methods and Risk Representation in Usable Privacy and Security Research", ACM ToCHI, 2021 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Consent Form

Description	Provide the consent form used to collect written consent from participants.
Applicable Study Types	Studies with participants that used written consent.
Reasons to Omit	A consent form may contain contact data of the researchers and thus have to be omitted or censored for the anonymous review process.
Priority	Recommended

Justification	The consent form can provide clarity on the exact terms that participants were presented with and agreed to, possibly indicating pre-study expectations or opt-out reasons of participants.
How-to	Provide the consent form as it was given to participants, ideally in PDF, Markdown, or similar format.
Preferred Reporting Location	Either within the appendix or as part of supplementary materials.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Study Compensation

Description	State if, how, and how much participants were compensated.
Applicable Study Types	Studies with participants.
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Compensation may influence who participates in a study and with what motivation, and therefore influence a study's results. Such an influence is an important context when interpreting results.
How-to	Report if, how and how much compensation participants were offered, and potentially how many of them accepted it, and how it compares to the average income of the studied population. Explicitly state, if participants were not compensated.
Preferred Reporting Location	Either within the ethics section or subsection (see Ethics), or in a section that describes the recruitment procedure that compensation was a part of.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022". CHI, 2023 "Common Pitfalls in Writing about Security and Privacy Human Subjects Experiments, and How to Avoid Them", SOUPS, 2010 "A Systematic Literature Review of Empirical Methods and Risk Representation in Usable Privacy and Security Research", ACM ToCHI, 2021 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Vulnerability Disclosure

Description	Describe if and how any vulnerabilities discovered during the research were disclosed.
Applicable Study Types	Studies that discovered vulnerabilities.
Reasons to Omit	In the case of ongoing disclosure processes it might be necessary to omit details – the fact that disclosure was considered/conducted should still be stated.
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	Vulnerability discovery, disclosure, and remediation are an example of study results' impact that may cause harm and should be mitigated. Therefore, it should be discussed as part of ethical considerations. They also underline the real-world relevance and impact of the findings.
How-to	Describe the disclosure process and its outcome(s).
Preferred Reporting Location	Either within the ethics section or subsection (see Ethics), or as a separate section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>During the course of this research, a vulnerability was identified in [system/software]. The vendor was notified on [date], and disclosure followed a responsible disclosure process. As of the time of publication, a patch has been made available.</i> • <i>Despite repeated attempts to contact the vendor regarding a privilege escalation vulnerability in XYZ OS, no response was received. We disclosed the vulnerability responsibly and provide limited technical details to avoid misuse.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	Authors' influence on the outcome of disclosure processes is limited, and vendor reactions are not necessarily a good indicator of research impact.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Anonymization/De-Identification

Description	Report utilized methods of data anonymization, de-identification or pseudonymization when applied to PII or otherwise sensitive data. This does not only apply to full datasets, but can also be necessary for aggregate data (e.g., demographics tables) or excerpts of data (e.g., a detailed quote from an interview) that might otherwise allow identifying someone. Both methods that are only used on published data and those used on all data before analysis should be described.
Applicable Study Types	Studies that collect PII or otherwise sensitive data.
Reasons to Omit	—

Priority	Recommended
Justification	Anonymization, de-identification, and pseudonymization techniques transform data and should therefore be described to help readers understand how the data differs from the original raw data. Describing these methods also provides clarity on how participants' data is protected.
How-to	Describe the utilized techniques, how they align with what participants consented to, and how they influence the data.
Preferred Reporting Location	Either within the ethics section or subsection (see Ethics), within a section describing qualitative or quantitative data processing, and alongside the published data in, e.g., supplementary materials.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>All personally identifiable information was removed, and quasi-identifiers were generalized to prevent re-identification. The dataset meets the criteria for anonymization under EU GDPR and is available in the supplementary materials.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	Protecting especially vulnerable participants has a high priority and may outweigh data utility. If really necessary, reviewers can request some insights as part of a confidential reviewing process, but some research cannot be conducted without strong privacy guarantees and must therefore accept limits on what can be shared.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022". CHI, 2023

Funding & Conflicts of Interest

Description	Declare who funded the project, as well as any other conflicts of interest.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Conflicts of interest may introduce biases or encourage emphasis of some results over others, and should therefore be declared.
How-to	Declare conflicts of interest, funding and grants. If appropriate, a contribution statement can help clarify which collaborators worked on what parts of a study and paper.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the acknowledgement section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	This might only be disclosed for a final camera-ready version of a paper because it might otherwise identify authors in the double-blind-review process.

Further resources	—
--------------------------	---

Sampling

Sampled Population

Description	Description of the target population that the study addresses and draws its sample from.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Stating the analyzed population gives important context to the results and any implications derived from them, and indicates what population(s) the results apply to.
How-to	Clearly state the targeted/analyzed population, and describe inclusion and exclusion criteria that determine whether an individual is part of the population.
Preferred Reporting Location	A “Sampling” or “Recruitment” subsection in the Method section; can also be already stated in the Abstract or Introduction.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“In our study, we investigate the behavior of Android Smartphone users.”</i> • <i>“We explore the perspectives of adults aged 65 and over living in the U.S.”</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	“Preliminary guidelines for empirical research in software engineering”, IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 2002

Sample Description/Demographics

Description	Describe any sample(s) used in analyses, including important sample characteristics such as demographic information.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	Sensitive data and studies with at-risk participants might require publishing only a subset of information, aggregated demographics, or even none.
Priority	Required
Justification	A sample description helps readers to contextualize results and assess how well and in which ways a sample represents a population. It can showcase diversity and highlight important characteristics that may influence the results.
How-to	Provide a table with important sample characteristics such as demographics, accompanied by some descriptive text. Ensure that data is sufficiently de-identified when dealing with sensitive data and populations or ask for explicit consent for publication in the consent form. If it is not possible to disclose sample description/demographics, briefly

	outline why.
Preferred Reporting Location	As its own subsection or part of a “Sampling” or “Recruitment” subsection within the methods or result section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	<p>Researchers should make sure to only collect relevant demographic information from participants that are needed to answer research questions and interpret or contextualize results.</p> <p>Typically, for many studies involving participants, demographics (e.g., age, gender, education, etc.) are the “standard” sample description. For those, describe how answer options were chosen, e.g., categories for ethnicity or gender, and number input or buckets for age. However, there might be situations and samples where other descriptions are appropriate.</p>
Further resources	<p>"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022", CHI, 2023</p> <p>"A practical guide to controlled experiments of software engineering tools with human participants", Empirical Software Engineering, 2015</p> <p>"Common Pitfalls in Writing about Security and Privacy Human Subjects Experiments, and How to Avoid Them", SOUPS, 2010</p> <p>"Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025</p>

Recruitment Approach/Sampling Strategy

Description	Describe the procedure(s) with which the study’s participants were recruited, or otherwise the means through which the data set was acquired. Include changes made to the approach during the study.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	<p>Describing the procedure for recruiting participants or creating data sets is required to understand and assess potential sampling biases. Including the initial strategy and explaining deviations helps clarify the recruitment goals and highlights changes from which researchers can learn about challenges and possible solutions. It also helps meta research such as: Engaging Company Developers in Security Research Studies: A Comprehensive Literature Review and Quantitative Survey, Usenix Security 2024</p>
How-to	Describe the recruitment strategy devised at the planning stage of the research project. Outline the procedure(s) used for recruiting/sampling, how many participants or data points resulted from each of them, and how long it took to achieve the final sample. Highlight and justify deviation from the original plan.
Preferred Reporting Location	A “Sampling” or “Recruitment” subsection in the Method section.

Description	Describe the procedure(s) with which the study's participants were recruited, or otherwise the means through which the data set was acquired. Include changes made to the approach during the study.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	Having to deviate from and extend initial recruitment plans is common and should not be penalized.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Preliminary guidelines for empirical research in software engineering", IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 2002 "A practical guide to controlled experiments of software engineering tools with human participants", Empirical Software Engineering, 2015 "Common Pitfalls in Writing about Security and Privacy Human Subjects Experiments, and How to Avoid Them", SOUPS, 2010 "A Systematic Literature Review of Empirical Methods and Risk Representation in Usable Privacy and Security Research", ACM ToCHI, 2021 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Sampling Materials

Description	Provide the materials used for sampling/recruiting (e.g., recruitment emails or posts, scraping scripts).
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	The materials or parts of the materials may have to be omitted during review to preserve anonymity. After acceptance, these should be added.
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	Having the actual materials provides details and fosters replication and reuse of resources.
How-to	Upload the materials in a format suitable to their nature as part of the supplementary materials, or add them to the appendix if feasible.
Preferred Reporting Location	Supplementary materials or appendix
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	Providing them as plaintext files (e.g., Markdown) ensures easy exchange and reuse.
Further resources	"Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Sampling Success Rate

Description	If possible, provide numbers for the success of their sampling strategy,
--------------------	--

	including number of invitations sent, accepted, rejected, and ignored, as well as drop-out rates during the study.
Applicable Study Types	Studies with applicable sampling strategies.
Reasons to Omit	Not all sampling strategies enable reporting a success rate, e.g., public posts do not show how many people have seen them.
<u>Priority</u>	Recommended
Justification	The sampling success rate provides information on the sampling procedure's effectiveness, and can provide insights on potential sampling biases. For future studies, insights into these numbers might help other researchers to plan their recruitment.
How-to	Share numbers for the success of their sampling strategy, including number of invitations sent, accepted, rejected, and ignored, as well as drop-out rates during the study.
<u>Preferred Reporting Location</u>	A "Sampling" or "Recruitment" subsection in the Method section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Preliminary guidelines for empirical research in software engineering", IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 2002

Sample Size

Description	State the sample size of a study, i.e., the number of valid participants/data points.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
<u>Priority</u>	Required
Justification	The sample size is vital to understand the scope of a study, and assess the validity of statistical analyses.
How-to	Clearly state the size of the sample. If reporting only valid data points, also make sure to include how many invalid data points were removed before analysis.
<u>Preferred Reporting Location</u>	A "Sampling" or "Recruitment" subsection in the methodology section; can also be already stated in the Abstract or Introduction.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>We interviewed 26 IT professionals.</i> • <i>Our final dataset includes 278 Reddit posts.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—

Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022". CHI. 2023 "Preliminary guidelines for empirical research in software engineering". IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering. 2002
--------------------------	--

Sample Size Justification

Description	Describe how the sample size number was arrived at, with references or reasoning explained (e.g., data saturation, power analysis).
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	A rationale for the sample size can help readers understand how the sample size does or does not support certain conclusions (e.g., generalizability).
How-to	Explain the rationale for the sample size, and include references to methodological concepts as appropriate. For quantitative research, the sample size is typically based on a power analysis to estimate what sample size is needed to detect effects of a certain magnitude with planned statistical tests. For qualitative research, sample size may be determined based on when data saturation is reached or based on sample stratification.
Preferred Reporting Location	A “Sampling” or “Recruitment” subsection in the Method section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>We stopped the recruitment process after 18 interviews, having reached theoretical saturation [cite].</i> • <i>We performed an a-priori power analysis to determine the required sample size. (Add explanations of parameters and assumptions used in the calculation.)</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Preliminary guidelines for empirical research in software engineering". IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering. 2002

Study Instruments and Materials

Experiment Materials

Description	Describe all materials and infrastructure used to conduct experiments, including tested interventions.
Applicable Study Types	Experiment studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Providing detailed experiment materials is essential for ensuring transparency, replicability, and verifiability of results. It also helps other researchers understand and replicate experimental conditions accurately.
How-to	Describe all materials and infrastructure used to conduct experiments, including tested interventions.
Preferred Reporting Location	Descriptions of the materials should go in a dedicated subsection within the methodology section, or in the appendix. Artifacts should be provided as part of the supplementary materials.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022" , CHI, 2023 "Common Pitfalls in Writing about Security and Privacy Human Subjects Experiments, and How to Avoid Them" , SOUPS, 2010 "Transparency of CHI Research Artifacts: Results of a Self-Reported Survey" , CHI, 2020

Interview Guide

Description	Describe and provide the interview guide or protocol used to conduct interviews during the research study.
Applicable Study Types	All studies involving qualitative interviews or (semi-)structured discussions/focus groups.
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Providing the interview guide ensures methodological transparency, aids replicability, enables external verification of the data collection approach. It also allows other researchers to adapt or refine these instruments for their own studies.
How-to	Clearly detail the interview questions, including the structure and format of the interviews (e.g., structured, semi-structured, unstructured). Describe the intended flow of the interview, specifying any probing questions or follow-up topics utilized. Additionally, explain the development process of the interview guide, for example, was

	derived from existing literature or refined through pilot testing. Finally, clearly indicate how and where the interview guide can be accessed, (e.g., appendix, supplementary materials, or an online repository).
Preferred Reporting Location	Dedicated subsection within the methodology or data collection sections, as an appendix or as part of supplementary materials.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022". CHI. 2023 "Transparency of CHI Research Artifacts: Results of a Self-Reported Survey". CHI. 2020 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations". IEEE S&P. 2025

Questionnaire/Survey Instrument

Description	Describe and provide all materials used to conduct experiments or interventions. This includes tasks, instructions, scripts, prototypes, software, hardware, or any other tools used as part of the study protocol.
Applicable Study Types	Studies with surveys or questionnaires.
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Transparency in surveys or questionnaires ensures replicability, facilitates the verification of results, and allows the research community to build upon validated instruments, thus enhancing the credibility of research findings. Moreover, it allows readers to contextualize results with the exact questions that were asked.
How-to	Include the full questionnaire/survey instrument in the appendix or online supplementary materials. Optionally, one can provide a short summary in the paper's methodology section.
Preferred Reporting Location	As part of supplementary materials, or within the appendix.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022". CHI. 2023 "Transparency of CHI Research Artifacts: Results of a Self-Reported Survey". CHI. 2020 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations". IEEE S&P. 2025

Data

Description	Provide the data collected during the study, ideally complete, raw data, or aggregated or anonymized data if necessary.
Applicable Study Types	All
Reasons to Omit	Raw data may contain PII or IP protected data, and cannot always be published. Protecting participants, their identity, and their data is very important, as is adhering to the procedure consent was initially obtained for. Data should not be published if it poses a risk to people or their rights.
Priority	Recommended
Justification	Data sets help to replicate analyses, and can be used for new analyses and comparisons of future research.
How-to	<p>Format the data in a way that makes it easy to access and process, and provide accompanying guidance on how the data is structured and should be used if necessary or helpful to understand it.</p> <p>Provide a brief description of the dataset, e.g., what data is contained, what the values in a table column mean, etc.</p> <p>Ideally, provide the data in an open, reusable/human-readable format (e.g., CSV) if possible.</p>
Preferred Reporting Location	In supplementary materials.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	<p>"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022". CHI, 2023</p> <p>"Promoting an open research culture". Science, 2015</p> <p>"Transparency of CHI Research Artifacts: Results of a Self-Reported Survey". CHI, 2020</p> <p>"Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations". IEEE S&P, 2025</p>

Analyzed Software

Description	Describe, and when possible, provide access to the source code of any software developed, modified, or used during research, including dependencies, configurations, and version information.
Applicable Study Types	All studies involving software tools, algorithms, or user facing systems.
Reasons to Omit	Specific details of software may fall under IP rights and can therefore not be published. It falls under the reviewer's discretion to decide if the paper's contribution is enough without it in these cases.
Priority	Recommended

Justification	Sharing software enhances transparency research, allows others to reproduce results, identify bugs or limitations, and extend work. It contributes to methodological rigor and supports open science practices within the community.
How-to	Describe the role and function of the software used in the study. Clearly state whether the source code is available and under license. Include relevant technical details (e.g., programming languages, version numbers, dependencies, required environments, and installation instructions). Also provide a working link where code is hosted and cite release if references are possible. Include a README file or similar usage instructions.
Preferred Reporting Location	In supplementary materials.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022", CHI, 2023 "Transparency of CHI Research Artifacts: Results of a Self-Reported Survey", CHI, 2020 "Transparency in Usable Privacy and Security Research: Scholars' Perspectives, Practices, and Recommendations", IEEE S&P, 2025

Analyzed Hardware

Description	Specify and provide the details of any specialized hardware or devices used, developed, or modified in the research, enabling others to replicate or build upon the work.
Applicable Study Types	Studies that depend on specific hardware or use custom or modified hardware.
Reasons to Omit	Specific details of hardware may fall under IP rights and can therefore not be published. It falls under the reviewer's discretion to decide if the paper's contribution is enough without it in these cases.
Priority	Recommended
Justification	Sharing hardware specifications ensures transparency, facilitates replication and verification of results, and supports researchers who seek to use, modify, or extend existing hardware-based studies.
How-to	Document the hardware components, specifications, or any related software dependencies required. Also, describe licensing or intellectual property considerations related to hardware sharing. Since actual hardware cannot be shared in digital format, schematics, 3D printing or assembly instructions can be ways to still share hardware. Include photos of hardware in the paper, if appropriate.
Preferred Reporting Location	In supplementary materials.
Example	—

Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Changes in Research Ethics, Openness, and Transparency in Empirical Studies between CHI 2017 and CHI 2022", CHI, 2023 "Transparency of CHI Research Artifacts: Results of a Self-Reported Survey", CHI, 2020

Qualitative Analysis & Results

Qualitative Data Preprocessing

Description	Describe how data was preprocessed prior to analysis, including transcription, translation, and anonymization.
Applicable Study Types	Qualitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Preprocessing transforms the data, and describing it in detail helps readers understand possible differences from the raw data.
How-to	Describe any preprocessing steps that were applied in sufficient detail to understand and replicate them, and software used for transcription or translation. This can also include inclusion or exclusion criteria when sampling from a larger set of data. Include if and how data generated by AI was detected and handled.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	Section 3.2 "During the analysis, we excluded 218 posts (8.58%) because they were irrelevant to online scams and were false positives" – Victims, Vigilantes, and Advice Givers: An Analysis of Scam-Related Discourse on Reddit, SOUPS 2025
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Qualitative Data Analysis Procedure

Description	Outline the methods and steps of the analysis procedure, and the role of the involved researchers.
Applicable Study Types	Qualitative Studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Understanding the analysis procedure is essential to understand how the results were obtained.
How-to	State the methods used, providing references where possible, and describe the steps in detail. Maintain and describe a record of key decisions, changes, or analysis steps throughout the study. This allows others to trace the evolution of the analysis.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	—

Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Different Researchers, Different Results? Analyzing the Influence of Researcher Experience and Data Type During Qualitative Analysis of an Interview and Survey Study on Security Advice" , CHI, 2023 Section 8, RQ2, and RQ3

Qualitative Analysis Software

Description	Share what software was used for data analysis.
Applicable Study Types	Qualitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Recommended
Justification	The analysis software shapes the analysis process and therefore provides helpful context, and self-written software can be reused and built upon by other researchers.
How-to	In case of third party software, state the name and version. In case of self-written software, provide the source code.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section in case of specifications; as part of supplementary materials in case of source code.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Qualitative Analysis Reliability

Description	Discuss how reliability was ensured, such as handling disagreements among researchers, calculating Inter-rater Reliability (IRR), or coding consistency or explain why IRR was not reported.
Applicable Study Types	Qualitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Providing reliability considerations helps to build trust in the analysis process.
How-to	Discuss how reliability was ensured, such as handling disagreements among researchers, calculating Inter-rater Reliability (IRR), or coding consistency. Provide rationales and references for decisions where possible.

Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	Not all types of qualitative analysis call for IRR (see the paper by McDonald et al.).
Other remarks	—
Further resources	"Reliability and Inter-rater Reliability in Qualitative Research: Norms and Guidelines for CSCW and HCI Practice". CSCW, 2019

Codebook

Description	Provide the final codebook.
Applicable Study Types	Qualitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Strongly Recommended
Justification	A codebook clarifies how themes were developed and ensures consistency of the results. It also supports reproducibility and credibility of findings, particularly when interpreting sensitive topics such as privacy concerns or security decision-making.
How-to	Provide your complete (anonymized) codebook with descriptions and applicable examples.
Preferred Reporting Location	As part of supplementary materials, or within the appendix.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Empirical Evidence

Description	Provide empirical evidence (e.g., quotes, field notes, excerpts, photographs) to support results.
Applicable Study Types	Qualitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Empirical evidence strengthens transparency, allows readers to assess interpretations, and showcases diverse voices and contexts.
How-to	Include representative quotes, photos, or excerpts that illustrate and

	support key findings or themes. Quotes should be attributed to participants via IDs while preserving anonymity if promised. Ensure balance between the views in the data.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the result section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	It can be particularly hard to remove identifying information from qualitative analysis results and materials. Reviewers should keep this in mind, when asking for open data in the case of qualitative studies.
Other remarks	Sharing empirical evidence does not necessarily mean to share all data, e.g., all interview transcripts. However, as qualitative work involves some kind of researcher interpretation, it is advisable to report some evidence and excerpts to give the reader a direct impression of the collected data.
Further resources	"Towards an Ethical Framework for Publishing Twitter Data in Social Research: Taking into Account Users' Views, Online Context and Algorithmic Estimation", Sociology, 2017

Quantitative Analysis & Results

Quantitative Data Preprocessing

Description	Describe any treatment of raw data prior to analysis, including outlier removal, variable transformation, data quality control.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Preprocessing transforms the data, and describing it in detail helps readers understand possible differences from the raw data.
How-to	Describe any preprocessing steps that were applied in sufficient detail to understand and replicate them, including used software and own scripts. Include if and how data generated by AI was detected and handled. The main paper should contain a short description on any preprocessing steps; details can be in some appendix or documented through software/scripts.
Preferred Reporting Location	Short description within the methodology section (or software as part of supplementary materials). More detailed description in an appendix.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“We removed incomplete survey answers from the dataset, as well as the ones who took longer than 10 minutes.”</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	Ideally, many preprocessing steps are automated with some script or software that is made available – as this allows reproducing the preprocessing.
Further resources	Section 5.2, specifically “Dependent and Independent Variables” in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers. SOUPS 2025

Quantitative Data Analysis Procedure

Description	Outline the methods and steps of the analysis procedure, including statistical tests.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Understanding the analysis procedure is essential to understand, assess the validity of, and replicate the procedure. Naming the specific method (e.g., regressions, chi-square test) clarifies the methodological approach and supports the validity of the results. It also allows reviewers and readers to assess the appropriateness of the method for the research question and data type.
How-to	State the methods used (e.g., name precise statistical tests and any

	corrections that were applied), providing references where possible, and describe the steps in detail. Make sure to specify whether a test is intended for paired or independent samples - some of the test names are otherwise similar (e.g t-test, Wilcoxon test). Identify whether tests account for repeated measures if relevant to the data. Maintain and describe a record of key decisions, changes, or analysis steps throughout the study. This allows others to trace the evolution of the analysis. One can also reference the used software package/tool.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A binary logistic regression was conducted to examine whether security warnings predicted users' likelihood of abandoning a task.</i> • <i>We applied a Bonferroni correction to account for multiple pairwise comparisons.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	Reviewing statistics can be challenging. If you are unsure, ask for missing information in your review or state to the other reviewers that you cannot check the details (e.g., as you are no expert). In that case, it is important that at least one other reviewer with sufficient expertise provides a review.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 5.2, specifically “Precise Test Name” in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers, SOUPS 2025

Quantitative Analysis Software

Description	Provide (self-written) code and scripts or specifications of third-party software used for data analysis.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies using software to analyze their data
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Recommended
Justification	Software tools provide structure to the analysis, directly affecting results and methodology. Certain software may also give slightly different results for the same statistical tests due to different randomization implementations, so knowing the software can aid in replication.
How-to	Specify the software used and describe how it was used during the analysis. This also pertains especially to self-written analysis scripts that are used to process data and compute results, etc. These should be made available as an artifact online through a long-term archival platform, and come with good documentation.
Preferred Reporting Location	As part of supplementary materials.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>We analyzed the data using Python and SciPy, providing all scripts and the dataset online at https://doi.org/XX.XXXXX/XXXXXXXXXXXX.</i>

Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	<p>"Promoting an open research culture", Science, 2015: Table 1, "Analytic Methods (Code) Transparency" (p. 1423)</p> <p>Sections 4-7 in From repeatability to reproducibility and corroboration. ACM SIGOPS Operating Systems Review Vol 49</p>

Variables

Description	Name and define all variables that are considered in the statistical analysis, and clearly label them as dependent or independent for each analysis they are a part of.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Precisely naming and defining statistical variables ensures that the analysis is interpretable, that operationalizations are transparent, and that findings can be reproduced or compared across studies.
How-to	Clearly name, define, and label all variables considered in the analysis. For categorical variables, state the categories within each variable, and which variable is the baseline (when relevant, such as for regressions).
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The dependent variable was task completion time, measured in seconds from the start to the end of each authentication task.</i> • <i>Independent variables included the security warning type (visual vs. textual) and user expertise level (novice, intermediate, expert), both treated as categorical variables.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 5.2, specifically "Dependent and Independent Variables" in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers. SOUPS 2025

Hypotheses

Description	Explicitly state hypotheses for studies that use confirmatory inferential statistics.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies with confirmatory inferential statistics.
Reasons to Omit	—

Priority	Required
Justification	Stating hypotheses increases transparency and allows for proper evaluation of study outcomes. They also distinguish exploratory from confirmatory analyses.
How-to	State hypotheses and link them to corresponding research questions and tests.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>H1: Increased password complexity leads to longer authentication times.</i> • <i>H2: There is a difference in perceived usability between the baseline and enhanced warning designs.</i>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 3.5.2 calls for distinguishing between <i>exploratory and confirmatory analyses</i> and reporting the “specific a priori consideration of the statistical methods and planned comparisons, in Improving transparency and scientific rigor in academic publishing, Journal of Neuroscience Research 2018

Assumptions

Description	State assumptions made for analyses, and how you tested or justified them.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Assumptions underlying statistical tests and if the data conforms to them provide important context to readers.
How-to	Explain all assumptions (such as normality of the data) made for each statistical test, as well as how you tested if they hold for the data you collected. Authors can also state that certain tests are robust to some assumptions (for example, two-sample t-tests tend to be robust to the normality assumption at sufficient sample sizes).
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the methodology section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 3.5.2: “Report normalization procedures, tests for

	assumptions”, in Improving transparency and scientific rigor in academic publishing. Journal of Neuroscience Research 2018
--	--

Descriptive Statistics

Description	Provide measures that describe your data set, such as a mean or median for the central tendency, a measure for variability, or percentages for categorical data.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	The data set is a key result of a study, and should therefore be described in as much detail as possible.
How-to	Write a paragraph describing your data set and its key characteristics. This may include the central tendency, a measure for variability, or percentages for important variables. You can support it with a graph showing the distribution of the data.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the result section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 5.2, specifically “Magnitude and Direction of Effects” and “Measures of Uncertainty, Variability, or Confidence” in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers, SOUPS 2025 Section 7, specifically recommendation to “Report non-standardized effect sizes and descriptives” in SoK: I Have the (Developer) Power! Sample Size Estimation for Fisher's Exact, Chi-Squared, McNemar's, Wilcoxon Rank-Sum, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank and t-tests in Developer-Centered Usable Security, SOUPS 2023

Correlations

Description	Describe correlations between the observed variables.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Recommended
Justification	Correlations between variables can lead to confounding effects, or might be interesting results themselves. They should therefore be identified and reported. Correlation or a lack thereof can be important for assumptions underlying statistical tests. Correlations in repeated-measures designs can also be used to calculate

	standardized effect sizes.
How-to	Describe which analyzed variables do and do not correlate, whether the correlation is positive or negative, and report the correlation strength.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the result section. Additional correlations, especially those which are not so large that the authors believe they influence the interpretation of the results, can be reported in the appendix.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	—

Statistical Results

Description	Report results of all statistical tests performed.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	The outcomes of statistical tests are important analysis results, as well as context for the resulting interpretations and conclusions.
How-to	Report all test results and values (such as F-values, R^2) for all tests pertaining to the research questions. A table can help to give readers a space efficient overview. Refer to the APA guidelines linked in further resources for reporting advice for specific statistical tests.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the result section. Tests that have less relevance for the research questions and the paper's main conclusions should be reported in the appendix.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 3.5.2 directs authors to include “a full account of the statistical outputs in the results section, in Improving transparency and scientific rigor in academic publishing, Journal of Neuroscience Research 2018 APA guidelines for quantitative research

Confidence/Significance Measure

Description	Provide measures for the statistical significance and confidence of statistical results.
--------------------	--

Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	Significance measures and confidence intervals provide valuable context for readers, and indicates the (un)certainty of statistical results.
How-to	Report measures such as exact p-values and confidence intervals around estimates of effect sizes for statistical results.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the result section.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	Finding no significant effect can be a valuable result that should be reported. Only accepting papers with significant results might lead to a publishing bias.
Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 5.2, specifically “Measures of Uncertainty, Variability, or Confidence” in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers, SOUPS 2025 Section 6 in Small, Medium, Large? A Meta-Study of Effect Sizes at CHI to Aid Interpretation of Effect Sizes and Power Calculation, CHI 2025

Report and Interpret Effect Sizes

Description	Report and interpret effect sizes of statistical results.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Required
Justification	The magnitude of an effect is important to indicate direction and whether it is relevant in practice. For example, there might be statistically significant effects but the corresponding effect size is so small that the practical relevance of the found effect is negligible.
How-to	Report the effect size together with statistical significance. Besides just stating the effect sizes, discuss and interpret them to set them into context. This can include e.g. using field-specific effect size guidelines [1], comparing to effects from related work [1] or highlighting practical consequences or limitations of effects [1, 3].
Preferred Reporting Location	In the results section (or discussion). Less important effect sizes might be reported in an appendix.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For reporting effect sizes: “From the figure we can observe that the differences in average comfort level between PII ($\mu = 2.4, \sigma = 1.45, 95\% \text{ CI } [2.3, 2.5]$) and general objects ($\mu = 4.0, \sigma = 1.16, 95\% \text{ CI } [3.9, 4.1]$) is large and significant ($p < 0.0001$).” –

	<p>"I am uncomfortable sharing what I can't see": Privacy Concerns of the Visually Impaired with Camera Based Assistive Applications, Usenix Security 2020</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For interpreting effect sizes, drawing conclusions from effect sizes: "We do not expect the observed gender effects of $\Delta_{male} = 0.28$ to impact the validity of our measurement as our study is in line with the current body of evidence for gender differences in self-efficacy, which further interact with cultural differences: Halevi et al. [56] reported a large gender difference in self-efficacy in the USA." – Home Is Where the Smart Is: Development and Validation of the Cybersecurity Self-Efficacy in Smart Homes (CySESH) Scale, CHI 2023
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	<p>Sections 5.6 and 6 in Small, Medium, Large? A Meta-Study of Effect Sizes at CHI to Aid Interpretation of Effect Sizes and Power Calculation, CHI 2025</p> <p>[Section 8 in A Qualitative Study on How Usable Security and HCI Researchers Judge the Size and Importance of Odds Ratio and Cohen's d Effect Sizes, CHI 2025</p> <p>Section 5.2, specifically "Magnitude and Direction of Effects" and "Model Fit" and Section 5.3 "Interpretation Recommendations" in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers, SOUPS 2025</p>

Explain Effect Sizes

Description	Explain effect sizes of statistical results.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies reporting effect sizes
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Recommended
Justification	Both readers, and authors from UPS papers may not be familiar with effect sizes (standardized or other) and as such have difficulties assessing effect sizes and drawing their own conclusions if they are reported without an explanation [2]. This is especially the case for effect size measures which are not commonly used, or which may not be recognizable as an effect size measure.
How-to	Provide a short definition of the effect size measures used for the hypothesis tests conducted in the paper. This could include with which tests or study designs the effect size measure is reported in the paper, an explanation connecting the standardized effect size to data characteristics like frequencies, mean differences or standard deviations, the minimum (no effect) and maximum possible values, if applicable, and whether directionality can be inferred from the effect size measure.
Preferred Reporting Location	In the data analysis or methodology section
Example	"Total Variation Distance (TVD),

	<p>defined as $TVD(P, Q) = 1/2 \cdot \sum_i P_i - Q_i$, is a standard metric for quantifying the distance between two distributions [24]. Intuitively, it corresponds to the fraction of respondents who answer differently between the two samples. A TVD of 0 indicates that two distributions are identical; as the distributions become increasingly disjoint the TVD approaches 1.” and remainder of subsection 3.3. Total Variation Distance. in Replication: How Well Do My Results Generalize Now? The External Validity of Online Privacy and Security Surveys, SOUPS 2022</p> <p>“Cohen’s d measures the difference between two means, normalized using the standard deviation, so that a Cohen’s d of 1 represents a difference of 1 standard deviation between the two means. Cohen’s d of 0 means the means in both groups are the same. The higher Cohen’s d is, the larger the difference between the means is.” from Section 4.10 in A Qualitative Study on How Usable Security and HCI Researchers Judge the Size and Importance of Odds Ratio and Cohen’s d Effect Sizes, CHI 2025</p>
Reviewer Guidance	—
Other remarks	—
Further resources	<p>Section 5.3, specifically “Make Results Intuitive” in Misuse, Misreporting, Misinterpretation of Statistical Methods in Usable Privacy and Security Papers, SOUPS 2025</p> <p>Section 8 in A Qualitative Study on How Usable Security and HCI Researchers Judge the Size and Importance of Odds Ratio and Cohen’s d Effect Sizes, CHI 2025</p>

Insignificant Results

Description	Report non-significant results.
Applicable Study Types	Quantitative studies
Reasons to Omit	—
Priority	Recommended
Justification	Not finding a statistically significant effect is a result that, while not providing evidence for an effect or a lack thereof, can help readers better understand a topic, contribute to meta studies, and inform the research and study design decisions of other researchers.
How-to	Report tests that produced non-significant results.
Preferred Reporting Location	Within the result section, or in an appendix.
Example	—
Reviewer Guidance	—

Other remarks	—
Further resources	Section 6 in Small, Medium, Large? A Meta-Study of Effect Sizes at CHI to Aid Interpretation of Effect Sizes and Power Calculation, CHI 2025